

THE ROLE OF PEDAGOGICAL PRACTICE IN DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCIES OF FUTURE PRESCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract. This article provides information on the forms of organization of the professional pedagogical practice of future educators of preschool educational organizations, the dual form of education, the importance of pedagogical practice, and the requirements for pedagogical practice in the formation of professional competence.

Keywords: future educator, competence, professional competence, form of education, dual education, pedagogical practice.

Аннотация. В данной статье представлена информация о формах организации профессиональной педагогической практики будущих педагогов дошкольных образовательных организаций, дуальной форме образования, важности педагогической практики и требованиях к педагогической практике в формировании профессиональной компетентности.

Ключевые слова: будущий педагог, компетентность, профессиональная компетентность, форма образования, дуальное образование, педагогическая практика.

In our country, improving educational processes and preparing students as high-quality, competent, and competitive specialists who meet labor market demands has been elevated to the level of state policy. For this reason, a number of reforms have been implemented in the field of education. In particular: The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “**On Education**” (new edition, 2020) defines the general foundations of all stages of the educational process, including the organization of practical training. The Law “**On the Status of the Pedagogue**” (No. O‘RQ-901, 01.02.2024) determines the legal status, rights, and responsibilities of teachers. Presidential Resolution No. PQ-289 (21.06.2022) focuses on measures to improve the quality of pedagogical education and to develop the activities of higher education institutions that train pedagogical personnel. Presidential Decree No. PF-73 (28.04.2025) is aimed at further improving the system of training pedagogical personnel. Resolution No. PQ-4749 (2020) concerns the establishment of pedagogical institutes in the regions and the formation of their practical training bases. Regulation No. 2938 (23.10.2017) defines the procedure for organizing pedagogical (qualification) practice within retraining and professional development courses for managerial and pedagogical staff of higher education institutions. Cabinet of Ministers Resolution No. 11 (08.01.2024) establishes the procedure for organizing paid qualification practice for higher education students. Cabinet of Ministers Resolution No. 900 (28.12.2024) regulates the organization of industrial

practice for students of vocational education institutions. Thus, a number of regulatory and legal documents have been adopted in this area. Qualifying pedagogical practice is considered the main foundational link in preparing a future specialist for the profession. Pedagogical practice serves as the first real “school of experience” that connects a student’s theoretical knowledge with the real working environment

Pedagogical practice aims to prepare future preschool teachers for their professional careers, enable them to apply the knowledge they have acquired in practice, develop a sense of responsibility for pedagogical activity, and cultivate the habit of self-improvement. It also involves learning the profession directly from a qualified specialist. Pedagogical practice is considered the first step toward the professional activity of future educators. It is applied in teacher education programs and is directed at improving pedagogical mastery. The professional training of future preschool teachers is carried out in close integration with pedagogical practice. The most important task of pedagogical practice is to develop and strengthen the professional competence of future specialists.

Based on the results of psychological research and the analysis of the presented ideas, we were able to clarify the essence and meaning of the concept of “competence.” From a psychological perspective, this concept refers to a specialist’s ability to behave appropriately in unfamiliar situations and circumstances, to build meaningful communication, to find new solutions in cases of misunderstandings arising in interpersonal relations, and to navigate effectively in ambiguous, contradictory information as well as in consistently developing and complex processes.

Competence requires a specialist to continuously develop and improve their knowledge, acquire new information, deeply understand social relations, search for necessary daily informational resources, and apply them effectively in professional activity. In conclusion, a professionally competent specialist clearly senses the demands of the time, strives for new knowledge, seeks and processes it, and applies it effectively in practice. Pedagogical practice expands and develops students’ intellectual potential by forming initial ideas about pedagogical activity, fostering curiosity, and relying on creative abilities. It is aimed at developing their knowledge and skills.

During the practice, students, under the guidance of experienced teachers, observe and study “Technology” lessons in general education schools. Through this process, they develop skills to assimilate teaching experiences, prepare planning documents related to professional activity, and learn how to effectively use them.

One of the key competencies developed in students during their professional (practical) training is professional competence. Professional competence is the combination of knowledge, skills, and personal qualities necessary for effectively performing professional tasks. It also includes students’ ability to apply their knowledge in various situations related to the subject. During the practice, students learn to analyze problems, make decisions, and take responsibility for the outcomes of their work, which is considered essential for their future professional activity. In

addition, the professional practice helps students develop personal competencies such as communication skills, teamwork, and critical thinking.

The administration and community of a preschool education institution play a significant role in the professional development of an educator. It is the responsibility of the institution's leadership to assign young educators to experienced teachers, allow them to observe lessons, and involve them in methodological association activities. In preschool institutions, great importance is placed on enabling future educators to work on self-improvement and continuously enhance their scientific, theoretical, and methodological knowledge.

In conclusion, during professional (practical) training, students develop creative and innovative skills, professional competence, and thinking abilities, which help them successfully adapt to the demands of their future profession. The modern labor market requires specialists to be flexible in responding to changes and to propose non-standard solutions. Additionally, students acquire skills such as developing educational materials for the subject of Technology and enhance various competencies, including conducting research, analyzing pedagogical methods, applying psychological approaches in the learning process, and managing the educational process effectively.

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